

Empowering the UK wheat community to achieve gender parity

End of Project Report

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Project Overview

There is a severe lack of female representation in wheat research particularly in academia at the independent career stage. Wheat is a critical staple, consumed by 4.5 billion people worldwide and the recent phenomenal advances in knowledge, tools and resources, have generated an absolute step change in the field that is needed to address current wheat insecurity. However, to achieve a wheat secure future will require that we not only embrace recent scientific advances but also accelerate the required shift in culture across the community to create a more supportive environment that embraces inclusivity and diversity to achieve the variety in scientific thinking that is essential to address these challenges.

To start addressing this, at the John Innes Centre (JIC) in partnership with The Sainsbury Laboratory (TSL) we initiated a mentoring programme in 2019 termed the “Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions” programme. This innovative mentoring programme is focused on supporting female postgraduate and postdoctoral early career researchers (ECRs) likely to pursue an independent career studying wheat. This hugely successful programme has supported an array of women to attain independent positions. In this current project supported by the United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) ‘Enhancing equality, diversity and inclusion in BBSRC-funded networks’ fund, we built on this strong foundation and harnessed the momentum we built to expand and cascade the programme across organisations within one of the largest coordinated wheat programmes in the UK, the Delivering Sustainable Wheat (DSW) Institute Strategic Programme (ISP; 2023 - 2028).

This BBSRC-funded project focused on supporting: (i) digitisation of the exceptionally valuable career development training courses previously developed by JIC/TSL Group Leaders (GLs) and enhancing accessibility to these courses through professional development of a publicly-accessible JIC training website (<https://training.jic.ac.uk>) to provide a platform for hosting course content, (ii) expanding the highly successful one-to-one mentoring programme at JIC/TSL to include female ECRs across the DSW network, (iii) providing professional female leadership training for ECRs delivered by [hfp consulting](#), and a dedicated career development workshop held at JIC/TSL with training provided by DSW GLs to enhance female ECRs preparedness for independence, and (iv) professional training of senior wheat researchers by [hfp consulting](#) in inclusive leadership to mitigate unconscious gender bias in recruitment and evaluation processes and to recognise and address organisational barriers that could be inhibiting female career progression. Implementing this programme across eight collaborating institutions (universities and institutes) from the DSW network, that represent the major organisations undertaking wheat research in the UK, will create the potential for significant transformative change in gender parity in the wheat research community in the UK.

Foundation

There are many women working in wheat research, but this representation is not reflected in senior leadership roles. With a plethora of female postgraduates and postdoctoral researchers working in wheat research across the UK, there should follow a better representation at the independent career stage. As seen across STEMM areas, gender is largely balanced at the onset of the postdoctoral period (men: 52%, women: 48%; **Figure 1**). However more women than men leave academia during the postdoctoral career stage, leading to an under-representation of women in senior roles. Although, women in academic careers as lecturers (43%) and professors (33%) are under-represented across STEMM, this is particularly acute in wheat research. This is in contrast to many other research areas where gender has or is becoming more balanced. For instance, in the UK within one of the largest coordinated wheat programmes – the Delivering Sustainable Wheat (DSW) Institute Strategic Programme (ISP; 2023 - 2028) – women represent only 22% of listed Co-I’s, declining from 24% in the previous Designing Future Wheat ISP (2017 – 2023). With so few senior female role models it is very difficult to break this inequality cycle.

To begin to tackle this issue, the Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions programme was established in 2019 as a collaboration between the John Innes Centre (JIC) and The Sainsbury Laboratory (TSL). This targeted programme consists of: (i) one-to-one mentoring provided by JIC/TSL Group Leader (GL) mentors who work with each female ECR mentee from the Norwich Research Park (NRP) institutes to develop clear actionable career plans, (ii) career development training sessions designed by JIC/TSL GLs to provide practical insight into the process of applying for independent positions and covering skill development to assist mentees in the next stage of their careers, (iii) career talks by external speakers to discuss their experiences and provide an overview of their career journey, and (iv) a two-day annual career development and networking workshop.

Prior to the onset of the current BBSRC-funded programme, 34 postgraduate students and 16 postdoctoral scientists had joined the mentoring programme. Of the 34 postgraduate students, 11 have since left JIC/TSL, with six securing leading positions in industry and others prestigious postdoctoral

fellowships (**Figure 2**). Among the 16 postdoctoral scientists – the closest career stage to independence – all six that have since left JIC/TSL attained independent positions, with five securing academic positions (independent fellowships and tenure-track positions, with half remaining in wheat research) and one establishing their own training initiative.

The exceptional success of this programme was also recognised by the Royal Society Rosalind Franklin Award in 2022. The implementation of this programme has started to shift gender inequalities in this field, whilst opening the conversation more widely across the wheat community in the UK and thus, starting to create a more supportive environment for women establishing their independent careers in this field.

Building on this foundation, the next step was to harness the momentum generated at JIC/TSL and markedly expand this documented success by cascading the programme across organisations within the DSW ISP and beyond with additional support from BBSRC.

Activities

1. Enhance access to career development resources developed at JIC/TSL. Through the “Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions” programme, JIC/TSL GLs developed numerous career development training courses that would be exceptionally valuable to implement across the DSW network. These courses are aimed at (i) preparing female ECRs for next career stages through development of their scientific identity and enhancing readiness for career transitions, and (ii) empowering them with leadership skills required for successful independent careers, whilst continuing to promote workplace inclusivity.

To facilitate distribution of these valuable training resources, we first enlisted professional support from [moonriver publishing Ltd](https://www.moonriverpublishing.com/) to further develop the JIC training website (<https://training.jic.ac.uk>) to provide a platform for hosting course content (**Figure 3**). A series of courses were then digitised, with each course designed to be downloaded and delivered by a local trainer at partner organisations and beyond. The courses were specifically tailored for early-career researchers (PhD students, post-docs, research assistants etc), with the aim for delivery to small groups, to enable individuals to learn through shared experiences. Trials of the courses at Rothamsted Research are currently underway, with the aim to develop a roadmap for wider adoption that can be added to the JIC training website to support further dissemination. Even prior to wider promotion, the JIC training hub website has already attracted 1.5K active users (**Figure 4**), with women in wheat course content gaining interest from people based in China, Singapore, UK, USA, Ireland and Venezuela. Inclusion of these resources in a public website, the development of an implementation roadmap and targeted promotion strategy will continue to facilitate broader use across the wider scientific community.

Figure 3. JIC training website as a hub for sharing training resources. (<https://training.jic.ac.uk>).

2. Widen access to career development mentoring across the DSW network. It is well recognised that increasing access to career mentors for women can have a substantial positive impact on productivity, formation of scientific identity, career satisfaction and success^{1,2}. Accordingly, a major contributing factor to the success of the “Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions” programme has been providing access for female ECRs to dedicated one-to-one career development mentoring.

Through this new project, we expanded this successful mentoring model to all female ECRs in the DSW network. Two calls for mentees were advertised for female ECRs to join the mentoring programme, with six new mentees enlisting from outside JIC/TSL. The pool of mentors was also expanded to include a wider breadth of the DSW network. All new GLs (mentors) and female ECRs (mentees) were provided with training from JIC/TSL around how to develop effective and supportive mentoring relationships.

As explained by Dr Catherine Evans earlier in 2025 “The mentorship has been a real boost for my career. I used the one-to-one mentoring to make my CV look as good as it could possibly be and I’ve used that in applying for postdocs. Now, looking ahead, the summer session has given me more clarity on how to go forward.”

These interactions continue to be central to supporting the career development of female ECRs within the DSW network, where mentees continue to secure independent positions. For instance, with two mentees in just the last few months obtaining and starting independent positions, one as a senior scientist and the other as a research group leader both in prestigious overseas organisations.

As Dr Anna Backhaus a former mentee, then trainer in the programme and now research group leader in the Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK) Federal Ex situ Gene Bank noted, “The power and impact of mentoring is too often invisible. I am glad the women in wheat training and JIC mentoring programmes have highlighted the importance it can have on careers and made mentoring more accessible to women across the UK. Being from a non-academic family background myself, it was highly valuable to have a mentor during my PhD that I could openly discuss all my questions with, especially the ones that weren’t fully formed ideas yet. Should I apply for this grant? Is this a good institute for a post-doc? Is my next publication or an outreach grant the better idea to pursue now? These are all difficult questions to answer when you are new to the world

of plant biology. Having a mentor gives you the possibility to discuss them, create new ideas, and mostly to gain that little bit of confidence needed to go on. I missed the initial deadline for the position I hold today, thinking I had no chance. Only after talking to a mentor of mine, I applied in the second round.”

Anna continued that “Another valuable lesson of the practical sessions on mentoring during the women in wheat training, in my opinion, is to learn that no one can, or has to, do it all alone. It’s okay to ask for help and advice, it’s normal to not know the answers, and no question is too silly to ask, no dream too big to discuss. This is also something I am now taking forward in my own mentoring style.”

It is also clear that the impact of the programme is not just limited to the mentees, as the mentors have equally gained valuable insight into the challenges faced by female ECRs that is leading to systematic change in the community. For instance, one of the mentors described how their involvement in the programme had 'crystallised' their awareness of gender representation in research. Subsequently, they were able to use their position to push for more diverse gender representation in meetings.

3. Enhance female ECRs preparedness and stimulus for achieving career goals in wheat research. To enhance female ECRs preparedness and confidence in attaining leadership positions in wheat research, it is essential that we support their professional leadership skill development and create a more inclusive and connected environment in the UK. In addition, it is well recognised that female-only leadership training enables women to clarify leadership ambitions and better recognise their leadership strengths³. Accordingly, when we previously implemented female leadership training at JIC/TSL, this was exceptionally well received (<https://www.jic.ac.uk/blog/training-the-next-generation-of-female-wheat-research-leaders/>).

Leadership training: Through this project we were able to support two professional female leadership courses provided by [hfp consulting](#) that included 29 female ECRs from 12 different organisations across the DSW network and beyond (**Figure 5 and Table 1**). This included 16 participants from 10 organisations outside the NRP (6 UK and 4 overseas) that had not previously had opportunities to be included in the programme. Within each workshop, participants explored a range of concepts essential for becoming an effective scientific leader, including active listening, time management, delegation, and conflict resolution. Participants were encouraged to shape each workshop, by choosing to delve deeper into the topics most relevant to their needs, particularly those with the greatest potential to enhance their leadership and teamwork aptitudes.

Participants found the interactive nature of the training workshops particularly powerful. Trainers and participants alike shared real-life leadership challenges, creating a workshop atmosphere rich in authenticity and reflection. Césarée Morier-Gxoyiya, a postgraduate research student from the JIC, commented: “Participating in a learning environment that fostered honesty and encouraged vulnerability was very helpful. It highlighted that many of our challenges are shared and promoted open discussions around which strategies would be most effective to further develop our leadership capabilities.”

Each course also provided an excellent opportunity for networking with fellow participants. Dr Manel Othmeni, a participant from the University of Nottingham, reflected: “It was one of the best courses I have attended! I learnt a lot and had the opportunity to meet a fantastic and inspiring group of female researchers.” Another participant added how “being in a group of competent and driven women was highly inspiring and fun!”

[See: <https://www.jic.ac.uk/blog/equipping-the-next-generation-of-female-leaders-in-wheat-research/>]

Figure 5. A subset of participants undertaking female leadership training at JIC/TSL with Prof. Diane Saunders and trainers from hfp consulting.

Career development workshop: We built on our previously successful annual career development and networking workshops (<https://www.jic.ac.uk/blog/inspiring-future-female-leaders-in-wheat-research/>) to broaden participation across the DSW network and beyond. Twenty-five participants attended the July 2025 training event (**Figure 6**), which included 11 participants from 10 organisations outside of the NRP (4 UK and 6 overseas) (**Table 1**). Support for all UK participants to attend the training course was covered by the BBSRC project, with costs for overseas participants supported by JIC and associated research projects.

Workshop trainers and facilitators included Diane Saunders, Simon Griffiths, Cristóbal Uauy, Paul Nicholson, David Seung, Darryl Playford, Thomas Hughes-Hallett (JIC), Nick Talbot, Sophien Kamoun, (TSL), Nichola Hawkins (Niab), and Anna Backhaus (ICARDA, Morocco and now IPK, Germany). Training modules covered (i) Creating your elevator pitch, (ii) Writing a fellowship proposal, (iii) How to prepare for an interview, (iv) Establishing and managing effective collaborations, and (v) Conflict resolution within teams. Over the two days, trainers and facilitators shared their own personal experiences and practical tips and guidance for participants. In addition, participants were provided with many networking opportunities to connect with their peers and trainers to support them in their career development and transitions.

Dr Chen Ji, a postdoctoral researcher at JIC, noted that “This training helped me clearly understand the differences between various fellowships, their requirements, and the application process. It also showed me how to prepare in advance. I believe this training was extremely valuable for both PhD students and postdoctoral researchers,”

The event also included a presentation from Royal Society University Fellow and Lecturer at Imperial College London, [Dr Jess Wade](#), on navigating academia’s hidden curriculum. The presentation highlighted the importance of academic mentoring in helping early career researchers identify the less visible ‘untaught’ topics that support successful research. As an advocate for promoting diversity in science, Jess shared her personal journey and her inspirational commitment to highlighting the careers of women and those from other historically excluded groups to advance diversity in science.

Dr Rose McNelly from JIC noted “Jess was a very captivating and engaging speaker and I came away feeling empowered to make science more accessible for those from underrepresented groups.” and Dr Lisa Lamberte from the University of Birmingham commented “What stood out most was her openness in acknowledging the hidden curriculum of academia — including how to network, how to interview effectively, and how to deliver engaging presentations. These are often unspoken skills, particularly inaccessible to those from backgrounds not traditionally exposed to academic environments.”

Through events such as the July workshop, the Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions programme provides a suite of skills and network approaches to equip and support women in their research career journeys. In doing so, these same activities foster greater visibility among women wheat researchers, and build a sense of community to pursue a career in wheat research.

The importance of the training workshop and the overall impact of this programme within the DSW network was clear in the comments from Dr Gillian Reynolds from the Earlham Institute, who said “I almost avoided being part of the wheat research community because of the low representation of women in senior roles, which didn’t foster a sense of belonging. With groups like Women in Wheat, we feel welcomed, we feel like we belong.”

[see: <https://www.jic.ac.uk/blog/women-in-wheat-event-provides-training-to-address-gender-bias-in-wheat-research/>]

Figure 6. Cross-institute career development and networking workshop, July 2025.

Table 1. Participants that took part in the female leadership training provided by hfp consulting and the cross-institute career development workshop. These courses specifically targeted early career female researchers.

Training	Dates	No. of participants	Participant organisations
Professional female leadership training	10th - 12th Feb 2025	14	John Innes Centre, Earlham Institute, Niab, Rothamsted Research, Aarhus University (Denmark) ¹ , CIMMYT (Mexico) ¹ , EIAR (Ethiopia) ¹ , KALRO (Kenya) ¹
Professional female leadership training	7th - 9th April 2025	15	John Innes Centre, Earlham Institute, Rothamsted Research, Imperial College London, University of Bristol, Lancaster University, University of Nottingham
Career development workshop	7th - 8th July 2025	25	John Innes Centre, Earlham Institute, Rothamsted Research, Niab, University of Birmingham, University of Bristol, CIMMYT (Mexico) ¹ , ICARDA (Morocco) ¹ , National Plant Protection Centre (Pakistan) ¹ , EIAR (Ethiopia) ¹ , KALRO (Kenya) ¹

¹Organisations located outside of the UK.

4. Create a gender aware and inclusive wheat research community in the UK. To reduce unconscious barriers to career progression for female ECRs we focused on delivering inclusivity leadership training for DSW GLs by [hfp consulting](#). Further building on the insight senior researchers had gained from their role as mentors, the aim was to provide the group with more in-depth knowledge, skills and tools to mitigate unconscious gender bias in recruitment and evaluation processes and recognize organisational barriers that could inhibit female career progression. Thus, elevating gender equity within teams and in institutional culture across the DSW network.

In late January 2025, twelve research leaders and senior staff from seven separate UK based institute and university organisations gathered at JIC/TSL to undertake leadership training specifically tailored for enhancing gender awareness (**Figure 7**). This included 6 female and 6 male participants from JIC (4 people), TSL (2 people), the Earlham Institute (1 person), Niab (1 person), Rothamsted Research (2 people), University of Nottingham (1 person) and the University of Lincoln (1 person). Over three days participants received practical training on inclusive leadership and were also guided in reflecting on their own current leadership style and personal experiences. This helped seed new knowledge and resources across multiple organisations across the UK wheat research community to enhance the collective ability to raise gender equity within teams and in institutional culture.

With so few female researchers in leadership positions in the wheat community, this training marked an important step towards enhancing the diversity in the community that is essential to achieve a wheat secure future. Dr Kim Hammond-Kosack, Group Leader at Rothamsted Research noted: “Although we are science leaders from different organisations and generations spanning three decades, this leadership training course clearly revealed that UK based female leaders in wheat research have faced and continue to face many similar challenges to achieve, remain and excel in their leadership roles.”

Kim continued “The collective experiences shared on this excellent training course by this cohort of women leaders and the strong peer support network established with male leaders during this training event, now provides a unique opportunity for the UK wheat community to address and gradually

change reoccurring themes that are clearly holding back UK female talent and wider diversity and inclusivity in wheat research.”

One element the group found particularly helpful was the opportunity to hear the lived experiences of the female participants. Professor Nick Talbot, Executive Director of The Sainsbury Laboratory, commented: “We have a long way to go to achieve a truly equitable environment for female scientists that provides opportunities and fairness at all levels. We should re-double our efforts to ensure that diversity and inclusion are values that we operate by in all aspects of our work. The course provided a forum to reflect upon best practice and positive behaviours in leadership. It was inspirational and important.”

Dr Clare Stevenson, Head of Science Coordination and Research Culture and chair of the Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity committee (EDI) at JIC, commented: “This training was excellent! It was not only thought-provoking, but also seamlessly integrated EDI and belonging into senior leadership tools and techniques. The cohort is now equipped and empowered to drive real change within their organisations, and the peer support network will be invaluable.”

Figure 7. Wheat research leaders undertaking inclusive leadership training at JIC/TSL with hfp consulting trainers, January 2025.

Additional activities

In addition to the BBSRC-funded initiative described above at JIC/TSL we continued with the core elements of the prior Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions programme, which within the project period (October 2024 –September 2025) included providing female ECRs working within wheat research and located at the NRP (i) continued mentoring to support their career development, (ii) two lunch and learn career development training sessions on “Getting the most from conference poster sessions” and “Optimising efficiency and productivity” and, (iii) five inspirational female career talks from speakers representing academia and industry to share their career journeys in sessions that were also open for other staff and students across the NRP to join. These additional activities were supported by JIC and TSL and dovetailed with the BBSRC-funded activities described above, further expanding the value of the programme.

Future directions and impact

This 12-month programme has already begun to strengthen the professional development of female wheat ECRs, empowering them with the confidence and tools for successful independent careers within wheat research. Specifically the BBSRC funding enabled us to: (i) provide exceptionally valuable professional leadership and career development training to our female ECRs, (ii) begin to broaden access to existing career development training resources through their digitisation and addition to a professionally designed training website, (iii) provide access to career development mentoring opportunities for female ECRs across the DSW network (particularly outside of the NRP), and (iv) heighten awareness of EDI and share good practice across DSW organisations through the inclusivity leadership training provided to GLs in the DSW network. The longer-term commitment within the DSW network to provide continuous mentoring to our female ECRs and their establishment of a supportive peer group, will ensure they are supported to achieve their career goals within the wheat research community. Thus, meaning we no longer continue to lose up to half our talent pool to other fields and can foster the variety in scientific thinking that is essential to address the challenges of wheat insecurity.

One future focus for the programme will be on continued diversification in leadership within the UK wheat research community. To date, we note that given the international nature of the wheat research community and the diversity of opportunities for our female ECRs, this has seen all those achieving independent positions and remaining in wheat research so far leaving the UK for prestigious opportunities overseas. As the gender balance across the wheat research community is skewed internationally this programme has made great advances in addressing the gender imbalance throughout the broader community. However, without a UK-focused retention strategy for these exceptionally talented female ECRs, the number of female research leaders in the UK wheat community will continue to decline as seen in the transition from the DFW to DSW programmes. Accordingly, the DSW network needs to collectively develop a strategy for our female ECRs to ensure the UK wheat community continues to equally diversify.

Part of this retention strategy will be the continued development of a more inclusive culture across the UK wheat community to accelerate the transformative change needed in gender inequality and beyond. This is underpinned by the research leaders that took part in this programme and continue to meet as a peer group and re-visit actionable changes that can be implemented at the array of institutes and universities in the DSW network. For instance, this group, which includes two institute directors, continue to informally meet and will revisit the learnings from the inclusive leadership course with hfp consulting trainers during a formal one-day workshop scheduled for February 2026. This will ensure inclusivity continues to remain central to the leadership across the DSW network and embedded at the core of all our research organisations.

Finally, we hope that freely sharing the training resources we developed, and our experiences within this programme, will create a roadmap that can be used for similar targeted implementation in other areas of need in future. We also look forward to following the career progression and continuing to support the phenomenally talented female ECRs that we have been fortunate to work alongside in this programme.

References

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